

SOCIAL FACTORS THAT LEAD TO THE EMERGENCE OF STUDENTS WHO LAG BEHIND IN MASTERING IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Annotation: This article describes a number of social factors that cause the occurrence of students who lag behind in learning, which are observed among primary school students today.

Key words: educational activity, mental activity, social activity, physical activity.

One of the problems facing our education system today is the inability of elementary school students to learn subjects well. The inability of students to learn subjects well and to acquire knowledge on an equal footing with their peers is not only a pedagogically studied problem, but today it is also a goal to study psychologically and socially the students who are lagging behind in their learning. considered appropriate work.

Studies show that during the period of primary education, reading activities take the place of playing activities. Learning becomes a child's task, social duty. In the process of studying, he learns the skills of keeping his textbooks and school supplies in order, getting up on time, going to school on time, and completing homework assignments. The student takes more and more responsibilities on his shoulders. The acquired knowledge increases the child's level, ensures his mental development, affects the growth of his senses and will. However, even during this period, the child's attention is still unstable. In primary school, changes occur in the student's memory. Starting from the first grade, the student voluntarily remembers most of the educational material during the educational process. At the same time, he should always control himself. As a result, the student's memory improves and his thinking grows. 7-8-year-old children still think concretely. They can only think about what they perceive or imagine. By this period, the first manifestations of logical thinking begin to form. In the third and fourth grades, students learn some concepts of scientific knowledge. During this period, emotional experiences occur in the psyche of students. Elementary school students develop an interest in a science or sport. They realize that education is a duty. A high assessment of the student's work during

the lesson gives rise to emotional experiences such as mental refreshment, joy, and pride in the students. However, there are also those who are lagging behind in subjects and whose mastery is rated low. It is necessary for each elementary school teacher to conduct individual work with these students and identify their shortcomings in time and find solutions to them as much as possible. Therefore, a teacher of primary education must be mature in all aspects, well-educated, a master of his profession, and a person with intellectual potential.

Children lagging behind in learning subjects have always been a problem for pedagogy, but in recent years, such problems can be included among the public problems not only in our country, but all over the world, which concern all pedagogues and psychologists. Attempts to solve it are reflected in the organizational steps implemented in the education system these years. Primary school students mainly include students aged 6-7 and 10-11 years old, and children of this age are classified as children of junior school age in psychology. We can observe a number of psychological problems in children of this age, as they are now transitioning from playing activities to educational activities. For example, they are easily distracted, cannot focus on one thing for a long time, are impressionable and emotional, and have difficulty following school rules. Because the students of the first grade find it difficult to sit at the desk for 1 lesson, and the relationship with the teacher and classmates seems to be very difficult for this age group. The fact that they feel uncomfortable in the group and cannot establish good relations with their classmates has a direct impact on their educational activities. There are basically four forms of student activity at junior school age, which are physical, social, mental, and academic activity.

Physical activity is a natural healthy need of the child's body to perform various physiological actions.

Psychic activity is the interest of a normally developing child in learning about objects and human relationships.

Social activity is the interest in knowing the relationships of people around them, the events happening next to them.

Activity in the educational process creates new conditions for the development of the child's behavior, requiring the child to develop speech, attention, memory, imagination and thinking at the appropriate level. The junior school period is a period of transition to conscious and voluntary behavior. Factors hindering the child's activity in the educational process are divided into 3 types: pedagogical, psychological and social.

Social factors that directly affect the child's learning process include the following;

Family is the main place in a person's life where he grows up and matures in all aspects. It would not be wrong to say that the family is the first school of every child. The first person a child sees when it is born is its parents. As the child grows up, his parents become an example for him in every way. It is said in vain that it is not necessary to educate a child, first let the parents educate themselves. But as they say, even rice cannot grow without wheat, not all parents can be role models for their children. An unhealthy environment at home, children under the care of a father or a single mother, disagreements between parents have an impact not only on the child's psyche, but also on his behavior. In order to solve problems in the family, it is necessary to establish cooperation between the school and the parents. In this case, the school psychologist teacher should conduct explanatory work and conversations with the child's parents.

Influence of students - in primary school, especially 1st grade students may have some difficulty adjusting to their classmates as they have just entered the school. It also depends on the individual characteristics of the student. Some students are enterprising and lively by nature, and some are shy and shy. Such students naturally have difficulties in establishing relationships with others. Such factors also cause the student to not learn subjects well. The class leader and the school psychologist have a great role in eliminating this.

Educational activity - the transition of 1st graders from playing activities to educational activities is a labor that requires a lot of patience and effort for them. First of all, the child should adapt to the school, class, teacher, classmates, course and training.

In conclusion, it should be said that any reasons and factors that lead to the inability of primary school students to learn subjects well, and if a solution is sought in time with the cooperation of the class leader, school psychologist and parents, the student will not have such problems in the future. will not be encountered again.

List of used literature:

1 Z. Nishanova, G. Alimova. Child psychology and teaching methods. "Union of Writers of Uzbekistan". Tashkent 2006

2 V. V. Ernazarova Educational psychology and its practical significance. European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. April - 2023 ISSN (E): 2720-5746. 366-369